

pupal, were present in AGM and were often found where the insect occurred (Fig. 1). The life cycles of the larval and pupal parasitoids are relatively the same as those which live in RGM (Fig. 2). The life cycle of *P. oryzae* synchronizes with the life cycle of the host. The life cycle of AGM is relatively longer (5-7 wk) than that of RGM (4-5 wk); the life cycle of *P. oryzae* on AGM is also longer than that on RGM (Fig. 2).

Based on biology and behavior, the *Platygaster* sp., which occurs as a dominant parasitoid of AGM, is now considered the complex of the *P. oryzae* of RGM. It attacks larvae of RGM, but attacks pupae of AGM because the parasite deposits eggs only when silvershoots of AGM emerge. ♂

2. Time of emergence of rice GM parasitoids.

Response of leaf folder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* G. to extracts of resistant *Oryza sativa* and *O. brachyantha*

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Extracts of rice and wild rice cultivars with LF resistance were obtained by steam distillation of leaves followed by diethyl ether extraction. The oily extract was diluted with acetone.

Freshly laid eggs were dipped in a 2,000-ppm solution and excess liquid drained. The eggs were incubated in petri dishes lined with moistened filter paper and the number of hatched and unhatched eggs recorded.

To assess larval response, 15-cm-diam petri dishes were divided into 6 compartments labeled alphabetically clockwise. Leaf pieces dipped in each variety's extract were placed in A, C, and E compartments; leaf cuts dipped in acetone were placed in compartments B, D, and F. Twenty-four 1st-instar larvae were placed at the center of each dish. After 24 h, the larvae settling on each leaf piece were counted.

Three-hour-starved 3d-4th instar larvae were offered leaves treated with the diluted oily extract and larval mortality determined.

TKM6 extract significantly reduced hatching, 57% unhatched eggs compared to only 8% unhatched eggs for the solvent alone (Table 1). Cultivars Kamalbhog, Darukasail, and TKM6 showed 32-36% larval mortality, significantly greater than the 2% mortality in control. The odor of TN1

did not influence orientation or settling response of the larvae, but on other cultivars, more insects responded to the odor of the control (Table 2).

Based on antibiosis, most of the observed cultivars are LF resistant. The chemicals are active against LF eggs and larvae. ♂

Table 1. Effects of extracts obtained from rice and wild rice varieties on LF, IRRI, 1986.

Source of extract	Accession no.	Unhatched eggs (%)	Larval mortality (%)
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101231	24 b	16 bc
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101233	35 b	12 bcd
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101234	39 b	8 d
<i>O. sativa</i>			
Darukasail	45493	20 b	32 a
Kamalbhog	49020	30 b	34 a
TKM6 (resistant check)	237	57 a	36 a
TN1 (susceptible check)	105	22 b	4 cd
Control (solvent only)	-	8 c	0 d

Table 2. Attraction of LF to leaves treated with steam distillate oils obtained from *Oryza* species, IRRI, 1986.

Cultivar	Accession no.	Insects (no.) after 24 h		Difference
		Treated with extract	Control	
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101231	22	63	41**
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101233	32	44	12**
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101234	39	46	7 ns
<i>O. sativa</i>				
Darukasail	45493	24	47	23**
Kamalbhog	49020	20	51	31**
TKM6	237	10	60	44**
TN1	105	37	57	19 ns